

. This survey is being conducted by Samuel Madureira Silva, a PhD candidate at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, working on testicular organoids as an *in vitro* model for the human testis under the supervision of Prof. Dr. Yoni Baert and Prof. Dr. Ellen Goossens.

Despite the increasing relevance of developmental and reproductive toxicology (DART) in chemical toxicity assessment, two important parts of DART are often overlooked or still do not have widely known/accepted *in vitro* models – **gonadal toxicity** and **placental toxicity**. The first relates to both the reproductive function, through gametogenesis, and endocrine disruption, through steroidogenesis and hormone receptor binding. The latter encases placenta and precursor structures, which are important in regulating the passage of substances to the developing foetus, as well as metabolising substances, toxifying or detoxifying them, and producing hormones.

With this survey, we aim to better understand the industry's current perspective on these two areas of DART, particularly regarding the application of *in vitro* New Approach Methodologies (NAMs).

The survey takes approximately 30 minutes to complete. However, it does not need to be finished at once - only make sure to re-enter the survey with the same device/browser to continue from where it was stopped.

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Q1. What is the main area of activity in your company?

- Industrial chemicals
- Pharmaceuticals
- Agrochemical products
- Cosmetics
- Contract research organization (CRO) services and/or method development
- Other

Q2. What type of toxicology activities are conducted?

- Mechanistic toxicology (focused on understanding the cellular, molecular, and biochemical mechanisms by which chemicals exert toxic effects)
- Descriptive toxicology (focused on toxicity testing to evaluate hazard for safety evaluation and regulatory requirements)

Q3. Do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Somewhat agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat disagree	Strongly disagree
Gonadal toxicity is an important area of toxicity assessment in the toxicology activities of your company.	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Placental toxicity is an important area of toxicity assessment in the toxicology activities of your company.

Q4. Do you use/recommend using *in vivo* models outside of general toxicology studies to predict **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation

Q5. What *in vivo* models do you use/recommend using to predict **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Rodents
- Dog
- Primates
- Other

Q6. What is the source of the *in vivo* models for **gonadal toxicity** assessment?

- In-house developed
- Guidelines
- Literature described
- Other

Q7. What is your level of confidence in the *in vivo* models used to conclude impact/safety in **human gonads**?

- Very high
- High
- Medium
- Low
- No confidence

Q8. What makes you choose/recommend these models to evaluate **human gonadal toxicity**?

- Regulators' demands
- Cost-efficiency
- Best models available for predicting human gonadal toxicity

In-house expertise

Mechanistic reasons

Other

Q9. Do you use/recommend using *in vitro* NAMs for **gonadal toxicity** and in which context?

Not used/recommended

Yes, regulatory testing

Yes, mechanistic investigation

Yes, screening/ranking of candidate chemicals

Yes, complement/refine the use of *in vivo* models

Other

Q10. What would make you choose/recommend (more) *in vitro* NAMs to evaluate **human gonadal toxicity**?

New regulations requiring new, animal-free models

More financial resources

Proven better models for predicting human toxicity

Different in-house expertise

Other

Q11. What is your view on using *in vitro* NAMs in **gonadal toxicology** for internal decision making?

Strongly supportive – *in vitro* NAMs offer faster, ethical, and reliable insights for internal decision-making.

Context-dependent – *in vitro* NAMs are suitable at certain stages but should complement traditional methods as these are still essential in internal decision-making.

Skeptical – *in vitro* NAMs may not fully replicate physiological systems and lead to loss of opportunities or carry translational risks.

Other

Q12. How soon do you think *in vitro* NAMs in **gonadal toxicology** will be used for regulatory purposes?

Should replace all *in vivo* studies **immediately** for regulatory purposes.

Should cover several facets of *in vivo* studies in the next **five years** for regulatory purposes.

At least **ten years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.

More than **twenty years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.

Will **never** cover all current *in vivo* data for regulatory purposes.

Other

Q35. Are you aware of any initiative/consortia tackling NAMs in the context of **gonadal toxicology**?

- Yes (please specify)
- No

Q13. Do you use/recommend using *in vivo* models outside of general toxicology studies to predict **human placental toxicity**?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation

Q14. What *in vivo* models do you use/recommend using to predict **human placental toxicity**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q15. What is the source of the *in vivo* models for **placental toxicity** assessment?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q16. What is your level of confidence in the *in vivo* models used to conclude impact/safety in **human placenta**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q17. What makes you choose/recommend these models to evaluate **human placental toxicity**?

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q18. Do you use/recommend using *in vitro* NAMs for **placental toxicity** and in which context?

- Not used/recommended
- Yes, regulatory testing
- Yes, mechanistic investigation
- Yes, screening/ranking of candidate chemicals
- Yes, complement/refine the use of *in vivo* models
- Other

Q19. What would make you choose/recommend (more) *in vitro* NAMs to evaluate **human placental toxicity**?

- New regulations requiring new, animal-free models
- More financial resources
- Proven better models for predicting human toxicity
- Different in-house expertise
- Other

Q20. What is your view on using *in vitro* NAMs in **placental toxicology** for internal decision making?

- Strongly supportive** – *in vitro* NAMs offer faster, ethical, and reliable insights for internal decision-making.
- Context-dependent** – *in vitro* NAMs are suitable at certain stages but should complement traditional methods as these are still essential in internal decision-making.
- Skeptical** – *in vitro* NAMs may not fully replicate physiological systems and lead to loss of opportunities or carry translational risks.
- Other

Q21. How soon do you think *in vitro* NAMs in **placental toxicology** will be used for regulatory purposes?

- Should replace all *in vivo* studies **immediately** for regulatory purposes.
- Should cover several facets of *in vivo* studies in the next **five years** for regulatory purposes.
- At least **ten years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- More than **twenty years** are needed to use them broadly for regulatory purposes.
- Will **never** cover all current *in vivo* data for regulatory purposes.
- Other

Q34. Are you aware of any initiative/consortia tackling NAMs in the context of **placental toxicology**?

- Yes (please specify)
- No

Intro models. When responding to the next questions, consult the following detailed tables with *in vitro* cellular/tissue assays available for gametogenesis, gonadal steroidogenesis, and placental function studies:

[DART survey - tables.](#)

Q22. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **oogenesis**.

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q23. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in*

in vitro model(s) for **oogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q24. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **spermatogenesis**.

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q25. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **spermatogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q36. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q26. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **ovarian steroidogenesis**.

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q27. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **ovarian steroidogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q28. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **testicular steroidogenesis**.

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q29. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **testicular steroidogenesis** study? (Please specify.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q37. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q30. Please attribute a personal level of acquaintance (either from using or reviewing data) and a personal level of confidence in safety translation to each model type below regarding **placental function**.

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q31. Do you use/have used any of these models? Do you use or are well acquainted with any other *in vitro* model(s) for **placental function** study? (Please specify.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.

Q38. In which regulatory framework(s) the development of these NAMs would be useful? (You may identify specific ones for different regulatory frameworks.)

This question was not displayed to the respondent.